

1 PhenoBR: a model to phenotype body 2 condition dynamics in meat sheep

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18 **Abstract**

19 In situations of negative energy balance (NEB) due to feed scarcity or high physiological
20 demands, body energy reserves (BR), mainly stored in adipose tissues, become the main
21 sources of energy for ruminants. The capacity to mobilize and restore such BRs in response to

22 different challenges is of major concern in the current context of breeding for resilience. Body
23 condition score (BCS) is a common, practical indicator of BR variations throughout successive
24 productive cycles, and quantitative tools for characterizing such dynamics at the individual
25 level are still lacking. The main objective of this work was to characterize body condition
26 dynamics in terms of BR mobilization and accretion capacities of meat sheep during their
27 productive lifespan through a modelling approach, using BCS measurements. The animal
28 model used in this work was the reproductive meat ewe ($n = 1478$) reared in extensive
29 rangeland. Regular measurements of BCS for each productive cycle were used as the indicator
30 of BR variations. A hybrid mathematical model and a web interface, called PhenoBR, was
31 developed to characterize ewes' BCS variations through four synthetic and biologically
32 meaningful parameters for each productive cycle i : BR accretion rate (k_b^i), BR mobilization
33 rate (k_p^i), plus the time of onset and the duration of the BR mobilization, t_b^i and ΔT^i ,
34 respectively. The model PhenoBR converged for all the ewes included in the analysis.
35 Estimation of the parameters indicated the inter-individual variability for BR accretion and
36 mobilization rates, and for the length of the mobilization period. The present study is a proof
37 of concept that the combination of data-driven and concept-driven models is required for the
38 estimation of biological meaningful parameters that describe body reserves dynamics.
39 Individual characterization of animals by these parameters makes it possible to rank them for
40 their efficiency in the use of body reserves when facing NEB challenges. Such parameters could
41 contribute to better management and decision-making by farmers and advisors, e.g. by
42 adapting feeding systems to the individual characteristics of BR dynamics, or by geneticists as
43 criteria to develop future animal breeding programs including BR dynamics for more robust
44 and resilient animals.

45 **Keywords:** mathematical model, body reserves' dynamic, body condition score,
46 challenge, ruminants

47

48 **Implications**

49 In situations of negative energy balances, the capacity of meat sheeps to mobilize and restore
50 their body reserves is of major importance in the current context of breeding for resilience. In
51 this respect, PhenoBR suggests a modelling approach to describe BCS dynamic with few
52 numbers of quantitative parameters at individual level. Such parameters could contribute to
53 better adapting feeding systems to the individual characteristics of BR dynamics, and by
54 geneticists as criteria to develop future animal breeding programs including BR dynamics for
55 more robust and resilient animals.

56 **Introduction**

57 Body energy reserves (BR) are the main source of energy in ruminants facing negative energy
58 balance (NEB) challenges such as highly demanding reproductive cycles or feed scarcity
59 periods (Bauman & Bruce Currie, 1980; Chilliard et al., 1998). The capacity of ruminants to
60 mobilize and restore such BRs in response to challenges is of major concern in the current
61 context of breeding for robustness and resilience, and for the ultimate sustainability goals of
62 farming systems. Resilience is defined as the capacity to recover after short-term
63 perturbations in the environment or changes in animal's physiological state, while robustness
64 is the capability of the animal to maintain its performance and deal with unfavourable
65 environments at long terms (Colditz & Hine, 2016; Friggens et al., 2017). However, it is worth
66 mentioning that these two terms are often interlinked and robustness at a given level is the

67 result of resilience at underlying levels. In this respect, priorities chosen by complex
68 mechanisms related to nutrient allocation and trade-offs become critical at the individual
69 level. BR administration and operational feeding strategies are among the main resources set
70 by the animal and the farmer, respectively, to cope with such challenges.

71

72 In meat sheep, a broad intra-flock variability in the dynamic of BR was shown during their
73 lifespan including several reproductive cycles. The genetic determinism related to the BR
74 changes has been demonstrated by considering successive physiological stages
75 independently (Macé et al., 2018, 2019). The BR dynamics could be considered in selection
76 strategies designed to improve the ewes' adaptive capacities while maintaining production
77 and welfare. It is therefore of major interest to phenotype ewes for their capacity of resilience
78 in situations of NEB.

79

80 Despite the importance of BR dynamics for animal robustness, its use in animal husbandry and
81 breeding is still at its very early stages (Friggens et al., 2017; Kitano, 2004). There are two main
82 reasons for this. Firstly, there is a lack of dynamic data describing animal response in a short-
83 , medium- and long-term perspective when facing different, successive challenges of different
84 magnitude and amplitude. However, progress in technology in the last decades has made it
85 possible to measure several indicators of animal performance with relatively high frequency
86 (i.e. dynamic records). Through the development of new technologies, the monitoring of
87 dynamic measures and indicators such as body weight (BW), milk yield and feed intake are
88 now possible with higher frequency and at lower cost. Secondly, the absence of synthetic
89 criteria for characterizing and quantifying BR dynamics is still a limiting factor for the use of
90 such a complex phenotype. Body condition score (BCS) is a practical and conventionally used

91 variable for monitoring BR dynamics. Compared to other variables such as BW, BCS is a proven
92 reliable indicator of the status of an animal's body fat reserves (Mendizabal et al., 2011; Russel
93 et al., 1969). Although some automatic advances are available, BCS continues to be a
94 subjective but effective variable, measured in general through direct observations carried out
95 by a trained observer (Pearce et al., 2009; Schröder & Staufenbiel, 2006). In outdoor farming
96 systems (e.g. grazing, rangelands, etc.) there are still limitations to overcome regarding, for
97 example, the availability of sound tools for implementing automatic measurement of BCS at
98 the individual level in open environments.

99 Subjective estimates of body condition have been widely used for a considerable time to
100 assess of fat in the live animal. Murray (Murray, 1919) defined body condition as 'the ratio of
101 the amount of fat to the amount of non-fatty matter in the body of the living animal. In the
102 method used in the experimental farm from which we collected the historical database
103 analysed in this study, the prominence of the spinous processes of the anterior lumbar
104 vertebrae is assessed by palpation (Russel et al., 1969). The sharpness and degree of cover of
105 the ends of the transverse processes and the extent of the muscular and fatty tissues beneath
106 them are then evaluated by spanning the lumbar vertebrae with fingers and thumb. Appraisal
107 of the depth of the *Mm. longissimus dorsi* and the degree of subcutaneous fat cover is made
108 by palpating the region between the spinous and transverse processes. A numeric score then
109 estimates, indirectly, body energy reserves in the animal, ranging from 'emaciated' (score 1)
110 to 'very fat' (score 5). In the specific case of females, this information indicates a strong link
111 with her reproductive performance, and the potential percentage of open females, lambing
112 interval, and lamb vigour at birth being among other parameters, all closely related to the
113 body condition of the ewe both at lambing and during the breeding season and lactation

114 periods. Finally, it is important to be aware that the particular characteristics of the breed can
115 have a strong influence on where and how body fat is deposited.

116 Macé et al.(Macé et al., 2018) concluded on the usefulness of BCS and BW data to study the
117 capacity of BR mobilization and accretion in meat ewes. Based on mean trajectories of BCS
118 and BW, they defined periods of mobilization and accretion throughout ewes' lifespans and
119 studied variations of BCS and BW in different physiological stages during these periods. Some
120 dynamic and mechanistic models were developed to predict fat fluxes in cattle during
121 transition periods, using BCS and DMI (Tedeschi et al., 2013) and to describe BR variations in
122 dairy goats during their lifespan using daily measurement of BW (Puillet & Martin, 2017).
123 However, to our knowledge, there is no tool still available for individual treatment of BCS data
124 in sheep to automatically detect periods of BR mobilization and accretion and to quantify the
125 related variability of individual responses to NEB challenges in a given common flock or
126 population.

127

128 The objective of the present work was to produce a quantitative, integrated tool to quantify
129 resilience capacity of meat ewes at the short term physiological challenge of reproductive
130 cycle. To this end, BR dynamics of meat ewes reared outdoors were characterized with a
131 small number of synthetic variables. To this end, a dynamic model, called PhenoBR, was
132 developed, based on a system of ordinary differential equations, as a support to describe BCS
133 variations in meat ewes over several productive cycles. This model is implemented in a web
134 interface (<http://adaptive-capacity.herokuapp.com/>) that lets users (even those unfamiliar
135 with modelling) test different hypotheses and results of the model. This tool should be very
136 useful for investigating physiological and genetic components of BR dynamics and developing
137 future animal breeding programs for more robust and resilient animals.

138

139 **Materials and Methods**

140 The animal model used in this work was the reproductive meat ewe, during its whole lifespan.
141 However, the model can be considered as generic and adaptable to other ruminant species
142 and productive purposes. The parameters of this model represent the ewe's characteristics
143 in terms of its capacities to mobilize and restore BR at each production cycle. Two main types
144 of parameters are expected. The first category comprises time-related parameters (i.e. time
145 related to the beginning of BR mobilization and the interval, or duration of the BR mobilization
146 period for each productive cycle). The second category of parameters relate to the intensity
147 of the BR mobilization period and the capacity to recover an expected BR status. The model
148 is hybrid in that it combines a data analysis procedure and a more concept-driven model.

149

150 **Animals and experimental data**

151 The datasets used in the present study have been previously described in detail (Macé et al.,
152 2018, 2019). Briefly, the experimental animals belonged to the Romane meat sheep breed.
153 The monitored ewes ($n = 1478$) were reared under extensive conditions on the rangelands of
154 the INRAE La Fage experimental farm (Causse du Larzac 43°54'54.52"N; 3°05'38.11"E,
155 Roquefort du Soulzon, France). Ewes performed one productive cycle per year. The biological
156 productive cycle length was thus 365 days. Data were collected for the period 2002 to 2015.
157 In this study, the BCS was used as the main indicator to illustrate the BR dynamics (i.e. the
158 capacity of ewes to mobilize and restore BRs). Ewes were measured for BCS, with eight
159 measurements collected regularly during each female's productive cycle according to a

160 physiological stage schedule. Ewes were measured during one to three entire productive
161 cycles (1278 ewes for cycle 1, 1204 for cycle 2 and 521 for cycle 3). All the ewes included in
162 the present study were pregnant and suckled at least one lamb until weaning (~80 days after
163 lambing). To assess BCS, the original grid described by Russel and coworkers (Russel et al.,
164 1969) was used and subdivided into a 1/10 scale, i.e. from 1 to 5 with 0.1 increments. As a
165 subjective method, considerable variations in score may be expected both between and
166 within observers. To reduce this variation, only two operators were performed the BCS
167 measurements throughout the entire period of the study. Even if in this work, no quality
168 control was performed, but to make sure of the reliability of BCS measures, the observers
169 performed regular quality controls with regular training sessions for adjustments and
170 calibration during that period. All the measurements were recorded in the Geedoc database
171 (<https://germinal.toulouse.inra.fr/~mcbatut/GEEDOC/>).

172

173 **Modelling procedure: General model**

174 To characterize the ewes' response to the increasing energy requirements at each productive
175 cycle in terms of BCS variations, a system of ordinary differential equations was developed.
176 For present purposes, the large increase in energy requirements during a productive cycle is
177 termed perturbation (physiological challenge due to pregnancy and suckling). The objective
178 of model development is to describe the ewe's response to that perturbation using BCS
179 variation as the indicator of ewe's response. Two interrelated state variables were used to
180 describe the ewe's response at productive cycle i : p_i for the decrease in BCS during the
181 mobilization period and BCS_i for the variations in BCS during the same productive cycle
182 including its decrease by p_i and its recovery (Fig 1). The driving force of this model is the
183 intrinsic capacity of the ewes to maintain or to restore their BRs to reach the expected BCS,

184 considered as the value of BCS in the absence of perturbations, noted BCS_m . The concept of
 185 the expected trajectory of performance is already described in the literature (Nguyen-Ba et
 186 al., 2020). In the database used, the ewe population attained at most three productive cycles,
 187 and the total BCS variations was calculated as the sum of BCS_i variations, for $i \in \{1,2,3\}$.

188
 189 Fig 1. The model for one productive cycle. Flux to BCS is regulated by the difference between BCS_i and
 190 the BCS_m for a given animal. The flux to p_i is activated in the interval $[t_b^i, t_e^i]$ and will stop when it
 191 reaches p_m . From the beginning of the perturbation, the decrease in BCS_i is counterbalanced by all
 192 internal physiological mechanisms of the ewes seeking to keep the BCS_i close to BCS_m .

193
 194 The general model for one productive cycle could then be written as Equation 1.

$$dBCS_i(t)/dt = \text{Accretion} - \text{mobilization} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

195
 196
 197
 198 For productive cycle i , periods of BR mobilization and accretion are both assumed to start
 199 from the point when BCS_i starts to decrease (t_b^i), considered as the starting point of the
 200 perturbation being studied. In this study, it is assumed that BCS is a good indicator of the ewes'
 201 BR variations, as previously demonstrated. When the animal is no longer able to meet the
 202 energy demands induced by pregnancy and lactation using only the energy available from

203 ingested feeds, it will mobilize the energy stored in its adipose tissues (i.e. its energetic BRs).
 204 However, during and after this period, the animal uses internal mechanisms to limit or to
 205 compensate for the quantity of BRs used during this period. This is illustrated by the effort of
 206 the animal to reach BCS_m . To clearly separate the effects of each productive cycle, the BR
 207 recovery capacity associated with productive cycle i starts at t_b^i and lasts until the beginning
 208 of the next productive cycle (t_b^{i+1}).

209
 210 The BR mobilization period is assumed to be over at t_e^i , which is the end of the BCS decrease
 211 period (i.e. end of perturbation i). t_e^i is associated with the point where the capacity of BR
 212 accretion surpasses the ewe's energy requirement. Equations 2.a and 2.b describe the
 213 variations in BCS_i and the simultaneity and continuity of BR mobilization and accretion
 214 processes for productive cycle i .

215

216 $dp_i/dt = k_p^i(p_m - p_i)$ for $t \in [t_b^i, t_e^i]$, Equation 2.a

217

218 $dBCS_i/dt = k_b^i(BCS_m - BCS_i) - k_p^i(p_m - p_i)$ for $t \in [t_b^i, t_b^{i+1}]$, Equation 2.b

219

220 Where k_b^i and k_p^i are the rates for BR accretion and mobilization during the productive cycle
 221 i , respectively. The constant p_m stands for the maximal loss of BCS due to the perturbation.

222 Variations in total BCS during the ewe's lifespan are the sum of variations of BCS_i at each
 223 productive cycle as stated in Equation 3.

224

225 $dBCS/dt = \sum_{i=1}^3 [k_b^i(BCS_m - BCS_i). (t \in [t_b^i, t_b^{i+1}]) - k_p^i(p_m - p_i). (t \in [t_b^i, t_e^i])]$

226

227 $BCS_i^{init} = BCS(day = t_b^i), BCS^{init} = BCS(day = t_b^1),$

228

229 $p_i^{init} = 0 ; P_m = 2$ unit of BCS ,

230

231 $i = 1,2,3$

Equation 3

232

233 where BCS_i^{init} is the initial value of BCS_i , and BCS^{init} is the initial value of the total BCS .

234 Using this model, the response of the animal at each productive cycle is characterized by the

235 set of parameters $\{k_b^i, k_p^i, t_b^i, \Delta T^i\}$, where $\Delta T^i = t_e^i - t_b^i$, and stands for the duration of the

236 mobilization period. Parameters k_b^i and k_p^i are estimated using the minimization function in

237 Equation 4

$$238 \quad f_{obj} = \min(\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^N [obs_j - BCS(t_j)]^2}), \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

239

240 where j stands for the number of observation points obs_j of BCS during the ewe's lifespan,

241 and $BCS(t_j)$ is the estimation of BCS at age t_j by the model (Equation 3). N is the number of

242 observations for a given animal (at most $N = 24$).

243

244 Other parameters of the model are time-related t_b^i and ΔT^i , which are determined using a

245 data analysis procedure for automatic detection of the perturbation within each productive

246 cycle. The dataset involved ewes with 1, 2 or 3 parities, and the data analysis procedure

247 allowed automatic determination of the number of parities to be considered for each ewe,

248 and the beginning and the duration of the associated perturbation.

249

250 **Modelling procedure: Automatic detection of perturbation period**

251

252 The beginning and end of each productive cycle were taken to be from one mating to the
 253 subsequent one. When all data were missing in a given period, it was taken as a missing
 254 productive cycle. In this section, a data analysis procedure based on functional data analysis
 255 (FDA) was developed to automate detection of perturbations within each productive cycle. In
 256 this procedure, the beginning of a perturbation (t_b^i) is where the observed BCS started to
 257 deviate from the initial value of BCS_i (BCS_i^{init}). The end of the perturbation (t_e^i) is where it
 258 started to recover.

259
 260 The expected value of BCS (BCS_m) is determined depending on ewes' maximum value of BCS
 261 (BCS_{max}). If $BCS_{max} < 3.4$ then $BCS_m = 3.5$, otherwise $BCS_m = 4$. The value of 3.4 was
 262 chosen because it was the common observed maximum BCS value for most of the ewes in the
 263 dataset. Also, in the construction of PhenoBR, the value of threshold BCS_m will be approached
 264 but never reached. It should therefore be larger than BCS_{max} , to let ewes reach their BCS_{max} .
 265 A B-Spline regression with smoothing parameters $\lambda = 10^3$ was fitted to the BCS data of each
 266 animal. This regression is in particular useful in cases where the general shape of the function
 267 under study is unknown, which is the case in the presence of perturbations. Equation 5
 268 describes the objective function to fit the B-spline function to observed data, for the
 269 estimation of the function $BCS(t)$.

$$270 \quad J_{obj} = \min(\sum_{j=1}^N [obs_j - BCS(t_j)]^2 + 10^3 \int_0^{t_{max}} [\partial^2 BCS(t)]^2 dt) \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

271
 272 Where obs_j stands for the j th observation of BCS, $BCS(t_j)$ is the estimation of BCS by the B-
 273 spline function and t_{max} is the last day of the BCS record for each individual. Zeros of the
 274 derivative of the estimated function $BCS(t)$ are maximums and minimums of $BCS(t)$.

275 This regression is drawn from methods on analysis of functional data (Codrea et al., 2011;
276 Nguyen-Ba et al., 2020; Ramsay & Silverman, 2002), in which the flexibility of the fitted
277 function is ensured by the use of the piecewise polynomial (in this case of degree 3) and the
278 smoothness is adjusted by the definition of a roughness penalty λ .

279 The parameter λ controls the goodness of fit versus smoothness of the estimated function.
280 For small values of λ , the estimated function $BCS(t)$ adjusts the data as well as possible by
281 reducing the squared error (first part of Equation 5). For larger values of λ , the second
282 derivative (second part of Equation 5) is penalized and which leads to small curvature of the
283 function $BCS(t)$. Ben abdelkrim and collaborators provided detailed explanations of the
284 method applied on both body weight and lactation curves (Ben Abdelkrim, Tribout, et al.,
285 2021).

286 Maximums indicate the beginning of potential deviations from BCS_i^{init} and minimums are the
287 beginning of the recovery period (Fig 2). A limited number of exceptions should be considered
288 if several extremums are present inside a productive cycle, or if there are no extremums,
289 (details of these cases are provided in hypothesis S1).

290

291 Although the procedure determined the beginning and end of the mobilization period t_b and
292 t_e , respectively, existing information on ewes' physiology were also considered for a more
293 reliable estimation of these values. In this respect, t_b can take a value approximately between
294 mating and lambing days, and t_e can take a value approximately between lambing and post-
295 weaning as defined in (Macé et al., 2018). In the construction of PhenoBR, the recovery period
296 of each productive cycle i is over when the next productive period starts ($t = t_b^{i+1}$). A major
297 challenge was then to determine the recovery period when second or third productive cycles
298 were missing for individuals from the original database. For this, it was assumed that in the

299 absence of t_b^{i+1} , the recovery from the productive cycle i would be over 150 days after the
 300 post-weaning period (i.e. the period corresponding to the next mating).

301
 302 Fig 2. Illustration, for one ewe, of the perturbation periods as determined by the data analysis
 303 procedure. t_b^i and t_e^i are associated with the times of the beginning and end of each perturbation.
 304 Dashed lines show the mating days of each parity as written in the original data set. Time zero
 305 represents the first BCS measurement.

306
 307 This procedure allowed the number of productive cycles and the associated t_b and t_e to be
 308 determined for each animal. All missing values of BCS were replaced by values of the function
 309 $BCS(t)$. Fig 2 illustrates the perturbation periods as determined by the data analysis
 310 procedure against a reproductive cycle as reported in the original dataset. Table 1 summarizes
 311 all parameters of the model.

312
 313 Table 1. Definition of different parameters and constants used in the PhenoBR.

Model parameters	Definition	Unit	Value

k_b^i	Rate of BR accretion during the perturbation and the recovery period of productive cycle i	1/ day	Estimation of the model
k_p^i	Rate of BR mobilization during the perturbation of productive cycle i	1/ day	Estimation of the model
t_b^i	Beginning of the perturbation in the productive cycle i	day	Estimation of the model
ΔT^i	Length of the BR mobilization period in the perturbation of productive cycle i	day	Estimation of the model
P_m	Maximum decrease due to the perturbation	Unit of BCS	2
BCS_m	Expected value of BCS in the absence of all perturbation	Unit of BCS	3.5 or 4 depending on the value of BCS_{max}
BCS_{max}	Maximum value of observed BCS for an animal	Unit of BCS	Determined individually from BCS records

314

315 The software R version 3.4.2 (R Core Team, 2017) was used for the development of PhenoBR,
316 estimation of the model parameters (function 'optim' of package stat) and for the data
317 analysis procedure (package fda). The structural identifiability of dynamic model (3) for
318 variables k_b^i and k_p^i was tested using the software DAISY (Bellu et al., 2007). The model was
319 structurally identifiable, meaning that the variable estimation problem is well posed and it is
320 theoretically possible to estimate uniquely the model variables given the available
321 measurements (Muñoz-Tamayo et al., 2018).

322

323 **Statistical analysis**

324

325 Since slight deviations from normality were observed for model parameters (k_b^i , k_p^i and ΔT^i),
326 Spearman correlation test was used to calculate the correlation among model parameters.
327 Analyses of variance were carried out, taking into account the repeated measures, with the
328 MIXED procedure of SAS (version 9.4; SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC), taking into account the
329 repeated measures to test relevant effects and interactions affecting k_b^i , k_p^i and ΔT^i (S1 code).
330 Fixed effects with $p < 0.05$ were considered as statistically significant.

331 Age at first lambing, parity of the ewe, litter size and year of measurement were identified as
332 fixed effects. The age at first lambing effect is the age at which ewes lambed for the first time
333 (i.e. 1 or 2 years; classes 1 and 2, respectively). The parity effect considered first, second and
334 third lambing (i.e. classes 1, 2 and 3, respectively). The litter size effect took into account the
335 number of lambs born and suckled by the ewe (i.e. singletons lambed and suckled for class 1;
336 twins lambed but only one suckled for class 2; twins lambed and suckled for class 3 and more
337 than two lambs lambed and suckled for class 4). The first-order interactions between
338 productive cycle and litter size and between age at first lambing and litter size were tested.

339 Cluster analyses had been previously performed to investigate the variability of BCS profiles
340 during each productive cycle (Macé et al., 2019). In the present study, the MIXED procedure
341 of SAS (version 9.4; SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC) was used to compare the parameters k_b^i , k_p^i
342 and ΔT^i for the different BR clusters. For each productive cycle, models included the cluster
343 factor together with age at first lambing, litter size and the year factors when needed.

344

345 **Software development**

346

347 To make the model easily usable by non-modellers, PhenoBR is also available as a web
348 interface on the free platform Heroku (<http://adaptive-capacity.herokuapp.com/>). The web
349 interface was developed using Python 3.7 (Van Rossum & Drake Jr, 1995).

350 Results

351 The PhenoBR fitting procedure to estimate parameters k_b^i and k_p^i converged for the 1474
352 ewes in this study ($f_{obj} = 0.54 \pm 0.22$ units of BCS, Equation 4). Four ewes with only one parity
353 and less than four datapoints were removed, because of lacking enough data for estimating
354 model parameters. The minimum and maximum of the residuals were 0.06 and 1.35 units of
355 BCS, respectively (S1 Fig). The dataset used in this study contained ewes with different number
356 of parities (from 1 to 3). To minimize the intervention of the user, PhenoBR enabled us to
357 identify automatically the number of reproductive cycles per ewe (1, 2 or 3), and in each cycle
358 to detect the time of the beginning t_b^i , and the length of the BR mobilization periods ΔT^i
359 ($\Delta T^1 = 212.3 \pm 51.0$, $\Delta T^2 = 174.6 \pm 53.4$, $\Delta T^3 = 181.1 \pm 50.2$ days). Descriptive statistics of
360 parameters estimated by the model are presented in Table 2.

361 Table 2. Descriptive statistics of parameters estimated in the modelling procedure.

	k_b^1	k_b^2	k_b^3	k_p^1	k_p^2	k_p^3	ΔT_1	ΔT_2	ΔT_3	f_{obj}
Mean	3.296	3.051	2.870	4.979	4.788	4.847	212.3	174.6	181.8	0.537
SD	1.034	1.110	1.078	1.704	1.661	1.401	50.9	53.4	50.2	0.222
Min	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.066	0.000	1.392	34.0	41.0	63.0	0.059
Max	7.755	8.548	8.613	14.349	16.485	10.494	341.0	338.0	372.0	1.355
1 st quantile	2.458	2.249	2.257	3.521	3.428	3.859	174.2	135.0	144.0	0.371
3 rd quantile	4.038	3.663	3.413	6.161	5.875	5.573	251.0	202.0	214.0	0.691

362 k_b^i and k_p^i are the BR accretion rate and BR mobilization rate during the productive cycle i .

363 Parameters k_b^i , and k_p^i are all multiplied by a factor of 1000 for better clarity. Parameter $\Delta T_i = t_e^i -$

364 t_b^i shows the duration of the BR mobilization period at each productive cycle i . The quality of model

365 fitness is shown by $f_{obj} = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^N [BCS_j - y(t_j)]^2}$ which represents the residual standard error of the

366 model.

367

368 Statistically significant positive correlations were found between parameters of BR

369 mobilization (k_p^i for $i = 1, 2, 3$) (Fig 3 ; details with scatter plots are provided in S2 Fig).

370 Positive and significant ($p < 0.005$) correlations between the BR mobilization rate (k_p^i) and BR

371 accretion rate (k_b^i) were observed for all three parities. Statistically significant negative

372 correlations between BR mobilization length ΔT^i and rate k_p^i could also be observed for

373 parities 1 and 3, i.e. the longer the BR mobilization period, the smaller the BR mobilization

374 rate.

375

376 Fig 3. Correlations between variables k_p , k_b and ΔT as estimated by PhenoBR for ewes' data set used

377 in this study. Grey and red shades stand for positive and negative correlations, respectively. All

378 correlation coefficients and p -values are noted. p -value, *** < 0.001 , ** < 0.01 , * < 0.05 .

379

380 Parameters k_b , k_p and ΔT were analysed for the effect of productive cycle, litter size, age at
381 first lambing and the year of BCS measurements (Table 3). Analysis of model residuals are
382 presented in S4–S7 Figs. Even if slight deviations from normality were observed in model
383 residuals, the large number of the sample under study enabled relaxing the normality
384 hypotheses of the residuals (Pek et al., 2018).

385 Statistically significant effects of cycle, litter size and age at first lambing were observed for k_b
386 and k_p . Values of ΔT were affected by the productive cycle and the litter size. A decrease was
387 observed for k_p and k_b , as productive cycle increased. Ewes had the longest period of BR
388 mobilization ΔT at productive cycle 1 and the shortest ΔT at productive cycle 2. As the litter
389 size increased, k_p and ΔT increased and k_b decreased. Ewes that lambed for the first time at
390 age one year showed lower k_b and k_p than ewes lambing at age 2 years. The interaction
391 between productive cycle and age of the ewes at first lambing could not be tested owing to
392 uneven distribution of ewes in the classes of each factor. Therefore, the effect of the
393 productive cycle was studied for each class of the age of ewes at first lambing (S1 and S2
394 Tables). Results showed similar effects of productive cycle to those described above except
395 for statistically non-significant effect of productive cycle on k_b in ewes lambing at age one
396 year.

397

398 Table 3. Summary of least-square means for the model variables (standard error) according to the
399 productive cycle, litter size and age of the ewe at first lambing

	<i>n</i> obs		k_p	k_b	Δt
Productive cycle	1278	1	5.14 (0.09) a	3.25 (0.03) a	212.96 (1.54) a
	1204	2	4.69 (0.09) b	3.06 (0.03) b	173.88 (1.52) b
	521	3	4.15 (0.10) c	2.73 (0.05) c	180.30 (2.32) c
		Sign.	***	***	***
	607	1	4.23 (0.10) a	3.25 (0.05) a	184.09 (2.18) a

	855	2	4.64 (0.10) b	3.04 (0.04) b	188.21 (1.94) ab
Litter size	830	3	4.78 (0.10) b	2.95 (0.04) c	190.23 (1.86) b
	712	4	4.99 (0.10) c	2.81 (0.04) d	193.64 (1.97) b
		Sign.	***	***	*
Age at first lambing	1390	1	4.45 (0.11) a	2.88 (0.03) a	188.04 (1.43) a
	1614	2	4.87 (0.10) b	3.14 (0.03) b	190.05 (1.35) a
		Sign.	***	**	NS
Year		Sign.	***	NS	NS
Productive cycle*litter size		Sign.	NS	NS	NS
Age at first lambing*litter size		Sign.	NS	NS	NS

400 n obs, number of observations; k_p , rate of body reserve mobilization; k_b , rate of body reserve accretion;

401 Δt , duration of body reserve mobilization period; Sign., significance; NS, non-significant. p -value, ***

402 <0.001, ** <0.01, * <0.05. Values of LS means with different letters indicate significant differences

403 between levels of each factor.

404

405 A previous study (Macé et al., 2019), using the ewes involved in the present study, showed

406 that ewes' BCS variations could be characterized by three classes of trajectory for each

407 productive cycle (graphs of different clusters are provided in S3 Fig). Ewes with similar

408 trajectories belonged to the same cluster. Major characteristics of these BCS trajectories

409 including BCS level, BCS loss and gain are given in Table 4 based on previous results reported

410 by Macé et al. (2019). The first productive cycle was characterized by clusters BC1, BC2 and

411 BC3, the second by clusters BC4, BC5 and BC6 and the third by clusters BC7, BC8 and BC9. The

412 two major clusters at production cycles 1 and 2 included 99% and 85% of the ewes,

413 respectively (clusters BC1, 63%; BC2, 36% and BC4, 55%; BC5, 30% respectively). In production

414 cycle 3, the major cluster (BC7) included 76% of ewes (BC8, 13%; BC9, 11%).

415

416 Table 4 summarizes the differences in k_b , k_p and ΔT between clusters at each productive

417 cycle. A statistically significant effect ($p < 0.01$) of clusters was observed for k_p at all three

418 parities. For parameter k_b , the effect of clusters was statistically significant at parities 1 and

419 3. Finally, only the clusters of parity 1 had a statistically significant effect on parameter ΔT .

420 The value of k_p was higher for ewes in BC3 at productive cycle 1, which is associated with
 421 ewes showing a marked and faster loss of body condition at the beginning of the BR
 422 mobilization period, compared to ewes in clusters BC1 and BC2. Values of k_b were higher in
 423 ewes belonging to BC1 and BC3 at productive cycle 1, clusters associated with ewes showing
 424 higher BR restoring capacity, compared to ewes in BC2. During the second productive cycle, a
 425 large difference in k_b was observed between BC5 and BC6. Cluster BC6 was associated with
 426 ewes showing the highest BR restoring capacity in the shortest lapse of time, and BC5 was
 427 associated with ewes that restored less BR in a longer period. During the third productive
 428 cycle, k_p was higher for BC9 and BC7, two clusters with ewes with similar BR dynamics
 429 characterized by a marked BR loss. The value of k_b was higher for cluster BC8 corresponding
 430 to ewes with the highest BCS levels throughout the third productive cycle.

431

432 Table 4. Summary of least-square means for the model parameters (standard error) according to
 433 clusters of ewes at each productive cycle.

Cyc	Cluster ¹	BCS	BCS	BCS	<i>n</i> ewes	k_p	k_b	Δt
1	BC1	medium	medium	medium	701	5.56 (0.14) a	3.37 (0.05) a	212.70 (2.21) a
	BC2	lowest	lowest	lowest	432	4.99 (0.14) b	3.12 (0.05) b	215.83 (2.51) a
	BC3	highest	highest	highest	9	7.18 (0.64) c	4.04 (0.37) a	152.01 (16.72) b
	Sign.					***	***	***
2	BC4	medium	medium	medium	593	4.82 (0.07) ab	3.19 (0.04) a	173.37 (2.22) a
	BC5	lowest	highest	medium	328	4.98 (0.11) a	2.83 (0.07) b	177.04 (3.12) a
	BC6	highest	lowest	highest	144	4.58 (0.14) b	3.73 (0.10) c	170.91 (4.47) a
	Sign.					NS	***	NS
3	BC7	medium	highest	medium	313	4.72 (0.10) a	2.91 (0.07) a	182.23 (3.30) a
	BC8	highest	lowest	highest	48	4.15 (0.22) b	3.72 (0.16) b	166.15 (7.18) a
	BC9	lowest	medium	medium	46	5.40 (0.37) a	2.89 (0.26) a	186.47 (7.65) a
	Sign.					**	***	NS

434 *n* ewes, number of ewes in each cluster; k_p , rate of body reserves mobilisation; k_b , rate of body reserves

435 accretion; Δt , duration of body reserves mobilization period; Sign., significance; NS, non-significant.

436 *p*-value, *** <0.001, ** <0.01. Values of LS means with different letters indicate significant

437 differences between clusters within a cycle.

438 ¹ Distribution of ewes in clusters and characteristics of body condition score (BCS) trajectories
439 throughout their productive cycle based on previous results reported by Macé et al. (Macé et al., 2018)
440 .
441

442 **Discussion**

443 The aim of the present study was to propose a metric of ewes' capacity to adapt to their
444 increasing and fluctuating energy requirements through several productive cycles. We
445 exploited the existing database derived from historical and dynamic measurements of BCS in
446 reproductive Romane meat ewes reared in an INRAE experimental farm in France to develop
447 a mathematical model, called PhenoBR. This model converts the individual time series data
448 of BCS into a small number of biologically meaningful synthetic parameters to characterize
449 body reserve dynamics of ewes.

450 Overall and individual body reserve trajectories had been previously described but without
451 characterizing the individual capacity of ewes for BR mobilization and accretion (González-
452 García et al., 2014; Macé et al., 2018). The model developed in the present study characterized
453 each productive cycle i with four parameters specific to each ewe: the BR accretion rate k_b^i ,
454 the BR mobilization rate k_p^i , the onset of the mobilization (i.e. onset of the perturbation
455 period) t_b^i and BR mobilization duration ΔT^i . These parameters, never described before, have
456 the potential to offer new indicators of BR dynamics in meat sheep and potentially in other
457 ruminants. The BR mobilization duration (ΔT^i), estimated in the present study, was consistent
458 with previous results and biological knowledge showing that BR mobilization lasted
459 approximately 180 days in our experimental conditions (i.e., almost 90 days in pregnancy and
460 90 days in suckling; Macé et al. 2018; 2019).

461 Although in this study subcutaneous adipose tissue, through values of BCS, was used to
462 illustrate the variations in BRs, it is well known that ewes have other sources of energy stored
463 in their anatomy in the form of adipose tissues (e.g. around internal organs, omental,
464 perirenal, inter- or intra-muscular tissues, etc.). Some breeds of sheep present also a
465 specificity to have a fat tail constituting an additional source of energy (Atti et al., 2004). This
466 diversity of adipose tissue sources (locations) can be mobilized in NEB situations (Chilliard et
467 al., 1998). Variations in the magnitude of lipid storage in such mostly internal adipose tissues
468 are undetectable by the BCS, which indicates only the status of the subcutaneous fat layer
469 depth. Therefore, when analysing the energy balance status of a given animal, caution must
470 be exercised when interpreting results from BCS alone, as BR mobilization may be in play
471 without a clear change in BCS. However, subcutaneous adipose tissue is considered as the
472 adipose tissue of most interest for investigating BR changes in ruminants since it is reported
473 to be the most labile adipose tissue, and BCS is closely correlated to total body fat content
474 (Russel et al., 1969). Thus the variables we propose in this study can be considered of high
475 relevance for BR dynamic characterization. Caution should be taken for the use of variables
476 quantified with PhenoBR for other adipose tissues than subcutaneous tissue because both
477 absolute contribution of different adipose tissues to total fat and their relative priority to be
478 mobilised have to be considered (Atti et al., 2004).

479 Moreover, considering the subjective nature of the body condition scoring, determining both
480 the repeatability and reproducibility (i.e. intra and inter-assessor repeatability, respectively)
481 of BCS measurements is important (Vasseur et al., 2013). In the case of PhenoBR, establishing
482 individual BR trajectories over successive physiological stages required a high level of
483 agreement with fine increments in the grid use to score BCS (0.25 points or lower). Insufficient
484 quality of BCS assessment will limit the detection of slight changes in BR over time.

485 Several models have been developed for converting time-series data into biologically
486 meaningful variables (Ben Abdelkrim, Puillet, et al., 2021; Friggens et al., 2016; Nguyen-Ba et
487 al., 2020; Sadoul et al., 2015). Some authors have proposed converting the longitudinal data
488 (such as BW, milk yield and BCS) of dairy goats into small number of variables, using a
489 mechanistic model describing priorities of dairy goats throughout their lifespan (Puillet &
490 Martin, 2017; Tedeschi et al., 2013). Other models have characterized animal responses to
491 different types of perturbations with approaches mainly based on data (Codrea et al., 2011).
492 The objective of all these models was to detect perturbations that affect animal performance
493 and health, and to characterize the animals' responses during such periods. When data were
494 available with high frequency, the models were able to detect periods of unknown
495 perturbations. The originality of PhenoBR compared to the existing models is its use of a
496 combination of a data-driven model (via FDA) and a dynamic model to detect perturbation
497 periods despite the limited number of available BCS records, and to subsequently characterize
498 ewe's response. Using the data analysis approach by fda helped to decrease the number of
499 variables to be estimated for the dynamic model and thereby increase the robustness of the
500 parameter estimation process (convergence of the process for all animals).

501 Several biological factors had a statistically significant effect on k_b^i, k_p^i and ΔT^i and were
502 similar to those affecting BCS when considered at a single time-point (Clawson et al., 1991;
503 González-García et al., 2014, 2015; María & Ascaso, 1999).

504 The decrease observed for BR mobilization rate k_p and BR accretion rate k_b (Table 3) as the
505 parity increased, indicates that body condition losses were more marked at the first
506 productive cycle during the BR mobilization period and gained more during the BR accretion
507 period, compared to productive cycles 2 and 3. However, results showed that for ewes

508 lambing at age one year (S1 Table), the effect of parity on their recovery capacity k_b was not
509 statistically significant. Given that they decrease their k_p as their parity increased, better
510 performance in ewes lambing at an earlier age could be expected.

511 According to BR mobilization and accretion rates, younger ewes at first lambing lost less body
512 condition and recovered at a lower rate than older ewes. This may be linked to the fact that
513 ewes at age one year are still growing and allocate less energy to adipose tissues to continue
514 their growth and assure their next reproduction cycle. The “round” nature of such growth in
515 younger ewes could induce biases in the BCS assessment as during palpation of the dorsal
516 region, the operator may recognize a larger and confounded mass of muscle and adipose
517 tissues. This is likely the case for the first BCS point in one part of our ewes present in the
518 database (S1 Table) for which the first BCS could be overestimated in comparison with the
519 same BCS or energy balance status in the following parities. The slope between this first BCS
520 value before mating and the following may be biased, which could affect k_p results in our
521 model (i.e. most drastic BCS variation).

522 Our results are consistent with those reported by Macé et al. (Macé et al., 2018) showing
523 similar effects of parity and age at first lambing when considering BCS changes between
524 successive physiological stages. The BR mobilization and accretion rates estimated in the
525 present study indicated that ewes were able to mobilize more BR as litter size increased, while
526 the BR accretion was less marked for ewes with larger litter size. The increase in BR
527 mobilization rate was expected because of the classical related higher energy requirements
528 for ewes suckling multiple litters. Similar effects of litter size on BR losses during pregnancy
529 and suckling had been previously reported when considering BCS differences between some
530 physiological stages (González-García et al., 2014, 2015; Macé et al., 2018; Walkom et al.,

531 2014). However, the decrease in BR accretion rate with the increase in litter size conflicted
532 with previous results showing higher BR accretion in ewes with higher litter size (Macé et al.,
533 2018). This discrepancy may be related to the fact that in the modelling, BR accretion starts
534 from the beginning of the perturbation, i.e. BR accretion rate was not only considered in the
535 recovery period but also during the theoretical perturbation period in which short anabolic
536 and catabolic reactions could be encompassed.

537 Interesting positive correlations were found for BR mobilization rates (k_p) between parities,
538 suggesting that ewes maintained their biological capacity for BR mobilization across
539 productive cycles. However, correlations between parities for the other two parameters
540 ($k_b^i, \Delta T^i$) suggested that BR accretion rate and BR mobilization duration varied across
541 productive cycles. This could be due to higher environmental effects of each cycle (i.e. feed
542 availability, number of lambs previously suckled, etc.) on BR accretion rate and BR
543 mobilization time. Correlations were also found between BR mobilization rate and BR
544 accretion rate suggesting both processes are biologically linked as previously claimed by
545 Chilliard et al. (Chilliard et al., 1998). This result was consistent with high genetic correlations
546 found previously between BR mobilization and accretion in the same dataset, which indicated
547 that ewes exhibiting high level of BR mobilization also exhibited high level of BR accretion
548 (Macé et al., 2018).

549 The variability in BCS profiles throughout ewes' lifespan had already been investigated by the
550 presence of clusters in each productive cycle (Macé et al., 2019). Each of these clusters were
551 characterized by BR trajectories differing in the level of BR and/or shape of BR changes
552 through the productive cycle. In the present results, we found consistency between average
553 values of BR mobilization and accretion rates and characteristics of BR profiles in clusters.

554 Differences between clusters found in the present study for BR accretion rate k_b and BR
555 mobilization rate k_p suggest that such parameters could be used for ranking animals according
556 to their BR dynamics. Thus PhenoBR offers an opportunity to investigate ewes' variability of
557 response at the individual level.

558 **Conclusions**

559 Farmers and advisers could use the average parameters quantified with PhenoBR to improve
560 and optimize feeding strategies and management at the flock level. For example, BR losses or
561 gains could be converted into energy units, for assessing energy balance at the individual or
562 flock levels. Thus, the feeding system of the flock could be adjusted to improve the BR
563 accretion or BR mobilization considering the physiological stage and different management
564 priorities. In addition, the existing inter-individual variability for BR mobilization and accretion
565 rates and duration of BR mobilization makes these parameters useful for ranking individuals
566 according to their BR dynamics. Such ranking helps at identifying extreme animals for BR
567 management compared to the average of the flock. Combined with their production
568 performances, this ranking contributes to the decision of keeping or culling animals.
569 Furthermore, combination of the individual characterisation of animals with PhenoBR helps
570 geneticists to select animals with better adjustment of BR dynamics to energy requirements.
571 Considering these new criteria for BR dynamics in the breeding objectives enables animal
572 breeding programs to refine selection strategies for more resilient animals. Combining these
573 traits with metabolic data, associated with BCS and therefore with the BR mobilization and
574 accretion processes, will enhance our understanding of mechanisms underlying animal
575 response to NEB perturbations. Altogether, in the perspective of developing resilient farming
576 systems, PhenoBR helps at taking advantage from ruminants' adaptive capacities when facing

577 successive NEB periods or other environmental perturbations affecting nutrient availability
578 and nutritional balances.

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587 **Ethics approval**

588 This study was conducted without carrying out any additional animal experiments or biological
589 sampling. The phenotypes used in the present study had been collected previously in other
590 projects that fully complied with applicable legislation on research on animals in accordance
591 with the European Union Council directive (2010/63/EU). All the experimental procedures
592 were performed according to the guidelines for the care and use of experimental animals and
593 were approved by the local ethics committee (approval number APAFIS4597-
594 2016031819254696).

595 **Data and model availability statement** The R script of ODE model and the dataset

596 used for this study are available in public repository Zenodo

597 (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4300412>). The web interface is freely available on
598 <http://adaptive-capacity.herokuapp.com/> .

599 **Declaration of interest**

600 The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

601 **Author contributions**

602 E.G. and D.H. designed the study and contributed to produce the database used in the current
603 work. M.T. and T.M. developed the model and data analysis procedures. G.K. and M.T.
604 developed the web interface. M.T drafted the manuscript. All authors contributed to the
605 analysis and interpretation of the results. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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719

720 **Supplementary Materials**

721 **S1 hypothesis**

722 For productive cycle 1, if t_b is not included between days 0 and 160 (i.e. approximately
723 between mating and lambing days) and t_e is not included between days 160 and 330 (i.e.
724 approximately between lambing and post-weaning):

- 725 - If no BCS maximum found, then $t_b=0$;
- 726 - If no BCS minimum were found between days 160 and 330 but there is a BCS minimum
727 before day 330 then $t_e=\text{day where BCS is minimal}$;
- 728 - If no BCS minimum found, then $t_e=360$;
- 729 - If two minimums found during the perturbation time, then $t_e= \text{day where BCS is}$
730 minimal.

731 For productive cycle 2, if t_b is not included between days 360 and 520 (i.e. approximately
732 between mating and lambing days) and t_e is not included between days 520 and 690 (i.e.
733 approximately between lambing and post-weaning):

- 734 - If no BCS maximum found between days 360 and 520 but there is a BCS maximum after
735 day 520 then $t_b=\text{day where BCS is maximal}$;
- 736 - If no BCS minimum were found between days 520 and 690 but there is a BCS minimum
737 before day 520 then $t_e= \text{day where BCS is minimal}$;
- 738 - If no BCS maximum found, then $t_b=360$;
- 739 - If no BCS minimum found, then $t_e=720$;
- 740 - If two BCS maximums found before the perturbation time, then $t_b = \text{day where BCS is}$
741 maximal;
- 742 - If two minimums found during the perturbation time, then $t_e== \text{day where BCS is}$
743 minimal.

744 For productive cycle 3, if t_b is not included between days 720 and 880 (i.e. approximately
745 between mating and lambing days) and t_e is not included between days 880 and 1050 (i.e.
746 approximately between lambing and post-weaning):

- 747 - If no BCS maximum found between days 720 and 880 but there is a BCS maximum
748 before day 720 or after day 880 then t_b = day where BCS is maximal;
- 749 - If no BCS minimum found between days 880 and 1050 but there is a BCS minimum
750 before day 880 then t_e = day where BCS is minimal;
- 751 - If no BCS minimum found, then t_e =1050;
- 752 - If no BCS maximum found, then t_b =720.

753 Some animals did not match the model correctly, so special conditions on the initial
754 parameters were set up for them so that they would be better represented.

- 755
- 756 - $kb1 = 0.001$ instead of 0.005 ; $kb2 = 0.002$ instead of 0.003 and $kp1 = 0.005$ instead of 0.003
- 757 - $kb1 = 0.001$ instead of 0.005 ; $kb2 = 0.001$ instead of 0.003 and $kp1 = 0.005$ instead of 0.003
- 758 Four animals with only one parity and with less than 4 points in the cycle or between t_b and t_e were
759 removed.
- 760

761 **S1 Table. Summary of least-squares means for the model parameters (standard error)**
762 **according to the productive cycle and significance of litter size, year and productive cycle x**
763 **litter size interaction effects in ewes performing first lambing at 1 year old.**

764

765 **S2 Table. Summary of least-squares means for the model parameters (standard error)**
766 **according to the productive cycle and significance of litter size, year and productive cycle x**
767 **litter size interaction effects in ewes performing first lambing at 2 years old.**

768

769 **S3 Table. Summary of least-squares means for the model parameters (standard error)**
770 **according to the clusters of adjusted BCS**

771

772 **S1 Fig. Histogram of the objective function (f_{obj}). Only a limited number of ewes with**
773 **$f_{obj}>1$ could be observed.**

774 **S2 Fig. Scatter plot of the model parameters. Deviations from linearity can be observed,**
775 **therefore Spearman method was used to calculate the correlation coefficients.**

776 **S3 Fig. Cluster profiles for the Body Condition Score (BCS) in Romane ewes over their**
777 **production cycles 1 (at the top), 2 (in the middle) and 3 (at the bottom) (from Macé et al.,**
778 **2018).**
779